

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

Application report of geospatial data process

Deliverable 4.4

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, D4.4 "Application Report of Geospatial Data Process," presents a comprehensive framework for the transformation, processing, and integration of diverse geospatial datasets within the AGEMERA project. As part of Work Package 4 (WP4), this document builds upon previous deliverables to establish a structured methodology for converting raw geospatial data into analysis-ready formats, ensuring compatibility with the AGEMERA platform. The report details the end-to-end workflow, from data acquisition via non-invasive geophysical methods to advanced data processing techniques, harmonization, and standardization for seamless incorporation into the AGEMERA data ecosystem.

The geospatial data collection process leverages a range of state-of-the-art technologies, including muon tomography, drone-based geophysical surveys, passive seismic measurements, and ground geophysical explorations. These diverse methods generate specific datasets, each requiring specialized processing techniques to ensure accuracy, consistency, and interoperability. This deliverable outlines the protocols for data acquisition, preprocessing, transformation into standardized formats, and finally visualization within the AGEMERA user interface.

A key component of this framework is the implementation of AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs), designed to automate and enhance data processing, fusion, and visualization. AIKPs facilitate the seamless integration of heterogeneous data streams into a unified platform, enabling efficient analysis and interactive visualization of complex geospatial datasets.

The AGEMERA platform provides a user-centric approach to geospatial data management, offering intuitive visualization tools that support the exploration of geological structures and mineral deposits. The platform's interactive web-based interface allows users to access, analyze, and compare multi-source datasets. Advanced visualization tools, including 3D viewing modes, lens and multi-lens tools, and layered data exploration, enhance the usability and interpretability of geospatial information.

By integrating cutting-edge technologies with standardized workflows, the AGEMERA project significantly advances the capabilities of geospatial data processing and its applications in mineral exploration. This document serves as a demonstration of the platform's potential. Moving forward, continued refinement of the AGEMERA UI and its associated AI tools will further empower researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers with enhanced capabilities for geospatial data interpretation and decision support.

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	2
Executive Summary	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Acronyms	5
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
1. Introduction and Objectives	8
1.1. Overview of work done so far in WP4	8
1.2. Scope of the Deliverable	8
2. Data Preparation for Application	10
2.1. Type of geospatial data collected during the project	10
2.2. Data collection and processing	12
2.2.1. Muon tomography	12
2.2.2. Drone-based geophysical surveys	18
2.2.3. Passive seismic measurements	20
2.2.4. Ground geophysical explorations	26
3. Development of Geospatial Applications	30
3.1. Overview of the geospatial applications (AIKPs) developed to process and visualize data sets .	30
3.1.1. Previously developed AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs)	30
3.1.2. Transforming and Visualizing Voxel Data using voxel AIKP	33
3.2. AGEMERA User Interfaces (AGEMERA UI) and tools	35
3.2.1 Examples of visualized data in AGEMERA UI	35
3.2.2 Standout AGEMERA AI tools and options	40
3.2.3 Data and access security	43
Conclusion	44
References	45

List of Acronyms

AGEMERA	Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials
1D	One-Dimensional
1VD	First Vertical Derivative
2VD	Second Vertical Derivative
3-C	Three-Component (seismic data)
3D	Three-Dimensional
AC	Autocorrelation
AIKP	Artificial Intelligence Knowledge Pack
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
ANT	Ambient Noise Tomography
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
COG	Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF
COS	Cloud Object Storage
COS	Cloud Object Storage
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
CSAMT	Controlled Source Audio Magnetotelluric
DB	Data Base
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
ELM	Equivalent Layer Modelling
EM	Electromagnetic
EO	Earth Observation
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group (coordinate reference systems)
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography
FG	Fluxgate (magnetometer)
GEM	GEM System (Manufacturer of magnetometers)
GeoJSON	Geographic JavaScript Object Notation
GeoTIFF	Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format
GGM	Ground Geophysics Measurements
GLB	Binary form of GLTF
GLTF	GL Transmission Format
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HG	Horizontal Gradient
HVSR	Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio
Hz	Hz – Hertz (Unit of frequency)
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
KML	Keyhole Markup Language
LAS	Log ASCII Standard (point cloud file format)
LAZ	Compressed LAS Format (point cloud file format)
LIS	Lund Imaging System
MSEED	MiniSEED (seismic data format)
NED	North-East-Down (directional coordinate system)

NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
nT	nano Tesla
nT/m	nano Tesla per meter
nT/m ²	nano Tesla per square meter
OCLI	Optoss Command Line Interface
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCD	Point Cloud Data (file format)
PDF	Portable Document Format
PosGIS	Spatial database extender for PostgreSQL
RGB	Red-Green-Blue (color composite)
RMS	Root Mean Square
ROI	Region of Interest
RSYNC	Remote Synchronization (file transfer utility)
RTP	Reduction to Pole
SAC	Seismic Analysis Code
S3	Amazon Simple Storage Service
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
TDR	Tilt Gradient or Tilt Derivative
TG	Total Gradient
TMI	Total Magnetic Intensity
TXT	Text File
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator (projection)
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WP	Work Package

List of Tables

Table 1. Two types of seismic stations deployed at Mina Concepción (LITHICA)

List of Figures

Picture 1. Shema of data collection, processing and visualization (OPT/NET)

Picture 2. Pre-processing workflow (Muon Solutions Oy)

Picture 3. Inversion workflow (Muon Solutions Oy)

Picture 4. Post-processing workflow (Muon Solutions Oy)

Picture 5. Typical anomaly pattern seen by a detector on a polar diagram (Muon Solutions Oy)

Picture 6. Screen shot of the visualization software developed by Muon Solutions that shows the bauxite lens targeted by the research (Muon Solutions Oy)

Picture 7. Processing workflow for Autocorrelations (LITHICA)

Picture 8. Processing workflow for Rayleigh Wave Ellipticity (LITHICA)

Picture 9. Processing workflow for HVSr (LITHICA)

Picture 10. Example of inversion of measured data on a tomographic profile in Krstače area. The absolute error for the sixth iteration is 10.1% (UZG)

Picture 11. Geometry of P-wave recording by seismic refraction on profiles with a length of 189 m (UZG)

Picture 12. Inverse velocity model for the RP-8 refraction profile measured around Krstače and seismic ray coverage model (UZG)

Picture 13. Examples of magnetic profiles around Mratnjača using measurements of the total intensity of the Earth's magnetic field. The profiles do not show magnetic anomalies originating from bauxite deposits but only anomalies from surface inhomogeneities and iron objects in the ground (Šumanovac et al. 2024)

Picture 14. STRATAGEM EH-4 – Transmitting antenna for generating an artificial electromagnetic field (UZG)

Picture 15. Voxel AIKP workflow (OPT/NET)

Picture 16. Electromagnetic drone measurements provided by RADAI (OPT/NET)

Picture 17. Monography measurement provided by MUON (OPT/NET)

Picture 18. Ground geophysics measurement provided by UZG as media files (OPT/NET)

Picture 19. Distribution of the factor of safety from 3D numerical model developed by CUP/KGHM for Lubin mine (Poland) (OPT/NET)

Picture 20. EGDl database as a base layer (OPT/NET)

Picture 21. Example of Sentinel-2 spectral indices (upper left), unsupervised clustering of a pair of Sentinel-1 images (upper right), Sentinel-1 visualizations (middle left), Sentinel-2 RGB composites (middle right), change detection based on 2 Sentinel-1 acquisitions (lower left) and Sentinel-2 PCA (lower right) (OPT/NET)

Picture 22. Lens and multi-lens tool in AGEMERA UI (OPT/NET)

Picture 23. Additional options available in AGEMERA UI (OPT/NET)

1. Introduction and Objectives

1.1. Overview of work done so far in WP4

Deliverable 4.1 (Data Processing Software with ML Algorithms for Spatial Data Processing) describes how the project uses several machine learning techniques like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and curvelet transforms to analyze and reduce data dimensionality. These methods help in identifying fault lines and generating structural maps for geological exploration.

Deliverable 4.2 (Workflow Process for Combining Datasets) outlines the data fusion process for integrating geological and geophysical datasets from multiple sources. It explains how the homogenization, integration, and fusion of data from Work Packages 1 and 3 contribute to a comprehensive understanding of geological features across trial areas.

Deliverable 4.3 (API Interface Specifications Report) lists various input, internal, and output file formats used in the AGEMERA platform. Key input formats include SAFE (for Copernicus Sentinel satellite data), GeoTIFF (for 2D geospatial raster data), and NetCDF (for 3D data). The platform also uses Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) and GeoJSON formats for storage and visualization of datasets and metadata respectively, ensuring compatibility and scalability across the platform.

1.2. Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable establishes a comprehensive framework for geospatial data processing within the AGEMERA project. It covers the entire workflow—from the initial measurement and off-platform data processing to the standardization of datasets into Analysis Ready Data (ARD) on the AGEMERA platform, ending in intuitive, interactive data visualization in the web-based AGEMERA UI.

This document serves as a practical demonstration of the platform's capabilities - how diverse data streams (including drone-based radiometric, magnetic, electromagnetic surveys, muographic imaging, and passive seismic methods) are integrated into a unified environment. This multisource fusion not only enhances the accuracy and reliability of geological interpretations but also facilitates rapid, informed decision-making for mineral exploration.

Picture 1. Shema of data collection, processing and visualization
OPT/NET

2. Data Preparation for Application

2.1. Type of geospatial data collected during the project

Important objectives of the AGEMERA project include the development of measurements and measuring methods for strategic mineral exploration and the demonstration of capability by results in selected research areas. The project incorporates several non-invasive geophysical survey methods, including passive seismic methods, drone geophysics (using electromagnetic, magnetic, and radiometric data), and cosmic ray muography. These methods are used to map subsurface structures and analyse mineral system footprints.

The integrated drone-based survey system of RADAI has been documented in AGEMERA WP3 deliverable D3.1. The results from **magnetic and electromagnetic (EM) surveys** are provided as GeoTIFF grid files. Initially, radiometric data were going to be presented simply as GeoTIFF grids of relative (total) gamma ray intensity (counts per second). Unfortunately, the radiometric system did not become operational (see D3.1). The magnetic data are processed using equivalent layer modelling, and the results are provided as maps of total magnetic intensity (TMI in nT) and some of its derivatives. The electromagnetic data requires one-dimensional (1D) or three-dimensional (3D) inversion, and the results are provided as maps of resistivity (Wm) at various depths. The field trials with the drone system so far include Naatikkalampi (EM only) near Kuusamo in Finland, Sniznica (EM+Mag) near Posušje in Bosnia-Herzegovina, and Rosen (Mag only) near Sozopol in Bulgaria. The field-trial over Asarel-Medet copper mine near Panagyuristhe in Bulgaria was unsuccessful. In Zambia three field trials (CBU, Luongo, and Mapatizya) were completed with the magnetic survey system.

Muography and muon-tomography, which is a relatively new method making its debut, will be an integral part of the AGEMERA project by mapping the density distribution of studied geological objects. The method can provide a uniquely sharp 3D image of geological objects thanks to mapping with relativistic muons characterised by straight trajectories, provided that the conditions for its application are met. The aim of the muographic measurements is therefore to estimate the high-resolution density distribution of the geological object under study, which can be the basis for the construction of geological models (ore bodies, fracture zones, etc.) important for mineral exploration, both from the point of view of stock estimates and extractability. The need for good spatial resolution is ensured by the high angular resolution of the muon telescopes used. The results of muon-tomography will also be included in the unified database for joint interpretation.

Lithica and CSIC have applied innovative **passive seismic methods** at Mina Concepción (Huelva, Spain) and Lubin Mine (Poland). Passive seismic is a relatively new approach in seismology that allows to convert seismic noise into signal. While Ambient Noise Tomography (ANT) is commercially used in the mining industry, our single-station methods—Rayleigh Wave Ellipticity (RWE), Autocorrelations (AC), and Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio (HVSr)—are novel in this context. RWE and HVSr generate 1D

velocity models beneath seismic stations, aiding in the detection of lithological changes and ore bodies. When deployed in a dense network, they enable the creation of 2D and 3D tomographic models. AC produces seismic traces that highlight subsurface reflectivity along a line perpendicular to major velocity contrasts. A dense linear deployment of stations can generate a 2D reflection seismic profile. Further details on these methodologies are provided in AGEMERA WP3 Deliverable 3.3.

UZG employed **Ground Geophysical Methods (GGM)** in investigating bauxite. Bauxite is a critical raw material that often occurs in complex geological environments, especially in karst deposits. GGMs play a key role in the exploration of CRMs, but their effectiveness in the discovery of bauxite deposits has not yet been sufficiently explored, especially in the Dinarides region. UZG focused its ground geophysical exploration (GGE) on karst bauxite deposits in the central Dinarides, particularly in the Jajce and Posušje areas (Bosnia and Herzegovina), where various geophysical techniques have been applied. These methods include Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT), Controlled-source Audio Magnetotellurics (CSAMT), seismic refraction and magnetometry. The investigations in Posušje comprised six micro-sites with extensive geophysical profiling over a total length of 13,883 metres. The Jajce surveys were also conducted at six sites, utilising ERT and CSAMT soundings. The main objective was to determine whether bauxite occurrences can be directly identified by characteristic anomalies in geophysical models and to evaluate the most effective methods for detecting bauxite in complex geological environments, which is documented in detail in AGEMERA WP3 deliverable D3.4.

In addition to the advanced geophysical measurements, AGEMERA UI has been populated with a range of **Earth Observation (EO) data derivatives** that significantly enhance the geospatial dataset portfolio. These EO products, derived from open satellite imagery such as Copernicus Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, include simple RGB composites, detailed spectral indices (e.g., NDVI, NDWI, and EVI), principal component analyses, change detection based on a SAR image pair, etc. By transforming raw satellite data into analysis-ready geospatial formats (like GeoTIFF), these derivatives provide surface information that complements subsurface geophysical data.

2.2. Data collection and processing

This chapter outlines the procedures used to convert raw geospatial measurements into formats ready for analysis and visualization on the AGEMERA platform. It provides a concise overview of the various innovative data collection techniques and applied processing steps. From muon tomography (MUON) and drone-based geophysical surveys (RADAI) to passive seismic measurements (LITHICA) and ground geophysical explorations (UZG), each subsection details the protocols for data acquisition, pre-processing, and transformation into Analysis Ready Data (ARD). By harmonizing these diverse datasets, the AGEMERA project ensures that complex geospatial information is accurately georeferenced, efficiently processed, and seamlessly integrated into the user-friendly AGEMERA UI.

2.2.1. Muon tomography

The most important element of the results is the discretized (voxelized) density distribution produced by muon-tomography, which will be transferred (after proper georeferencing) to the OPT/NET database in the format defined in the AGEMERA project documentation, thus allowing for appropriate visualization and supporting further processing and geological interpretation.

Density values (e.g., in 3D voxels) are referenced to the range covered by the mapping cones of the muon telescopes, for a 3D equidistant grid aligned to geographic coordinates. A voxel is entered into the database by the coordinates of its centre and the density of rock volume associated with that voxel.

Data processing

3D results can be obtained, for example, by processing and inversion of measurement data from precisely positioned and oriented muon telescopes. This procedure works as follows:

Pre-processing

The aim of the pre-processing procedure is to determine the direction-dependent density length distribution (muon trajectory-based density integrals) for each telescope position. It will be the input array of inversion procedure.

The main steps of pre-processing are:

1. Estimation of particle trajectories based on ionisation trace detected in a multi-chamber detector (telescope). In this phase, the separation of the low-energy muons and other particles (that cannot be used in tomography) is performed. The identified high-energy muon trajectories can be characterized by fitted azimuth and zenith in the detector coordinate system.
2. Directional classification of trajectories (directional discretisation), i.e. the derivation of a directionally discrete distribution of muon counts.
3. Determination of detector acceptances related to directions and the trajectory determination algorithm.

4. Determination of the variance of muon counts, assuming a Poisson probability distribution.
5. Determination of the directional distribution of muon flux from counts, corrected for measuring time and detector acceptance.
6. Coordinate transformation between detector frame and local geographic coordinate system (the global coordinate system is handled in the later part of the procedure).
7. Determination of the elevation dependent surface reference muon flux distribution (Lesparre et al.).
8. Determination of the direction-dependent density length from the directional flux attenuation (Lesparre et al., D Reyna)
9. Calculation of density-length propagated variances.

Pre-processing – muographic measurements

Picture 2. Pre-processing workflow
Muon Solutions Oy

Inversion – tomographic density distribution estimation

Inversion is a tomographic estimation of the internal density distribution of a geological object from measurements taken at the surface of the object using proper statistical criteria. In the data processing we have defined, the transformations involving nonlinear elements are decoupled from the inversion process, so that they can be performed in a simpler linear form.

Main steps of inversion process are:

1. Filtering the input density length data system by reliability.
2. Derivation of a topographic model of the area (DEM).
3. Generation of a topographic model of the detector environment (mine shaft/tunnel surfaces).
4. Generation of a voxel network covering the object of interest (or the target).
5. Calculation of the sections of mapping cones of the muon telescopes and the voxel network (determination of the Jacobian matrix of the inversion problem)
6. Simulation and sensitivity studies to determine in advance the efficiency of a given measurement setup. These are also used to optimize the voxel network.
7. Determining the focal range of the measurement system.
8. Building a prior density model of the geological object.
9. Bayesian-type density distribution estimation using the prior model, which is a parameter fitting with Bayesian regularization in L2 norm.
10. Graphical check of fit.
11. Preparation of result files: format and frame transformation.

Inversion – muon-tomography

Picture 3. Inversion workflow
Muon Solutions Oy

Note that the muon-tomographic method is necessarily a biased estimate, which means that it shows 3D geometry changes of the density distribution, but it flattens the true density contrasts. The bias can only be corrected to a limited extent.

Post-processing

The aim of post-processing is to highlight and identify the structures that emerge and to visualize them to aid geological interpretation.

Key steps are:

1. Use of filtering procedures to detect coherent (spatially contiguous) structures or even structure boundaries.
2. Categorization: identifying structures with different characteristic densities.
3. Format (CDL and NetCDF format) and coordinate transformations (WGS84 – UTM) for loading into a unified database. This database allows information from different sources to be handled together.

Picture 4. Post-processing workflow
Muon Solutions Oy

Data visualization

The visualization of muographic data has several important functions:

- Measurement verification and quality control
- Control of data processing quality and settings
- Overview: large scale visualization of data
- Visualization of results for supporting geological interpretation
- Display of interpretation results (multilayer 3D visualization)

The different performance charts and related time series for quality control of measurement and data processing are available at the activity performer carrying out the measurements and data processing. Muon Solutions ensures that they are available and stored. These diagrams and plots are usually linked to a detector and a measurement campaign. The measurement results linked to angular bin structure can be visualized in polar plot (both in the detector's own coordinate system and in the local geographical system).

Picture 5. Typical anomaly pattern seen by a detector on a polar diagram
Muon Solutions Oy

The tomographic results obtained from the combined processing of the muographic measurements can be displayed in 3D voxelized form. The voxels are oriented according to local coordinates, as is the surface model. The voxel results can be checked using 3D visualization software developed at Muon Solutions.

Picture 6. Screen shot of the visualization software developed by Muon Solutions that shows the bauxite lens targeted by the research
Muon Solutions Oy

Interpretation requires rotatable, zoomable visualization. The 3D results transformed into global coordinates and the geologically categorized version of the results are available in the OPT/NET database. This is linked to the necessary visualization interface, allowing a more accurate geological interpretation and comparison with other results. This can help to understand geology more accurately and to determine the extent of the location of the explored resource as a geological object.

2.2.2. Drone-based geophysical surveys

The results from RADAI's drone geophysical radiometric, magnetic, and electro-magnetic (EM) surveys are provided as GeoTIFF grid files. The georeferencing is made in geographical 2D (longitude, latitude) coordinates over WGS84 ellipsoid (EPSG: 4326). Separate metafiles (TXT files) provide relevant background information of each GeoTIFF grid.

The radiometric data are presented simply as a maps of relative gamma ray intensity (counts per second). The pre-processing of radiometric data is made using RadaiView software. After completion of the survey, the daily data area combined, interpolated, and saved in a grid format using a suitable third-party software (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS or Surfer).

The preprocessing of magnetic data is made using RadaiView software. The pre-processing involves, for example, computation of projected (UTM) coordinates, profile distance, and height (barometric and GNSS) above ground. Preprocessing also includes fluxgate sensor calibration to account for the effects the drone itself imposes on the magnetic data, and the base station correction that accounts for the natural, daily change of earth's magnetic field during the survey.

The post-processing of magnetic data is made using the equivalent layer modelling (ELM) in RadaiPros software. It makes tie-line correction to level the datasets made with different drones-fluxgate sensor combinations, heading correction to find out the level difference between lines flown in opposite directions, and micro-levelling that aims to correct the remaining, usually striped artifacts in the magnetic data. At the final stage the ELM is used to apply the corrections on the magnetic data and, optionally, make altitude correction and final tuning on the magnetic data. A suitable third-party software (e.g., ArcGIS, QGIS or Surfer) is used to grid the final tuned total magnetic intensity (TMI in nT) data and to create the GeoTIFF grids.

The ELM can also be used directly to 1) compute TMI on an even grid at an even height above the ground, 2) make upward and downward continuation, 3) reduce the data to the pole (RTP correction), and 4) compute derivatives of the magnetic data. The derivatives include the first vertical derivative (1VD, nT/m), the second vertical derivative (2VD, nT/m²), horizontal gradient (HG, nT/m), tilt gradient or tilt derivative (TDR, degrees), and total gradient (TG, nT/m) also known as analytical signal. The purpose of the derivatives is to enhance the information content of magnetic maps to aid visual (qualitative) and structural interpretation of magnetic data. The RTP correction, for example, can be considered compulsory for any surveys made at low latitudes (near the equator) where earth's magnetic field is nearly horizontal. The RTP correction will transform the magnetic maps so that peak anomalies are seen above their sources. All the abovementioned derivatives can also be computed using Fourier transform with a suitable third-party software (e.g. Oasis montaj, Geoscience Analyst, or RADAI's Fourpot).

The processing of the electromagnetic (EM) data requires the greatest amount of work. The raw EM data consists of in-phase (real) and quadrature (imaginary)

components of the magnetic flux density (B-field, in pT) in north, east and down (NED) direction at three frequencies (2.3, 4.6, 9.2 kHz). For EM data, the in-phase component is that portion of EM total field data that is in the same phase as the primary EM field (transmitter current). Likewise, the quadrature component represents the part of the EM field that has 90° phase lag with in-phase component. Presently only the ground loop transmitter is operational, and to “illuminate” the study area or targets from different directions it is necessary that the same survey area is measured several times using different transmitter loop locations. All in all, EM surveys produce multiple overlying datasets which by themselves do not provide information about the geology of the survey area. Because one-dimensional (1D) inversion does not comply with fixed loop system if the geoelectrical structure is complex, three-dimensional (3D) inversion must be applied to create a 3D resistivity/conductivity model of the entire survey area.

The processing and inversion of drone EM data is made using RADAI’s Lempo3D software. Lempo3D can be used to read in the raw EM data, clip the data inside survey area, divide the data into separate survey lines, smoothen/filter the data, and resample/interpolate the data with even sampling step. Lempo3D can also convert the EM data into different response form. Since presently the phase calibration of RADAI’s Louhi EM device is not working properly, the ratios (B_e/B_u and B_n/B_u) between the amplitude of east (B_e), north (B_n) and up (B_u) are used in the 3D inversion.

The 3D inversion is based on an approximate integral equation solution (Pirttijärvi et al, 2002), which has been extended from thin plate conductors embedded in conductive 2-layer earth to fully 3D problems. The block-like 3D model bodies can be considered either as solid bodies with constant resistivity or mesh models with internal resistivity variation. The inversion of the resistivity of a mesh model utilizes the adjoint solution of McGillivray et al. (1994) to determine the Jacobian (sensitivity matrix) with minimal computational cost. The EM inversion also uses an Occam-type of constraining for model roughness.

Despite the many approximations used in the EM modelling and inversion, computation of the EM response is time-consuming. On a typical desktop computer, single inverse iteration can easily take an hour even if the amount of data has been restricted around the most interesting parts of the study area (1-1.5 km²). Therefore, rather coarse models are used where the element size is equal to line separation (50-75 m) and the depth extent is limited to 3-4 layers. The results of the EM inversion are presented as grids of resistivity of the model layers (units in Ωm) from different depths (0-300 m). Since the resistivity values range over several decades (1-10000 Ωm), the grids are presented as the 10-base logarithm of resistivity (0-5 $\log_{10} \Omega\text{m}$).

2.2.3. Passive seismic measurements

Passive seismic methods output 1D georeferenced property distributions. Data are provided as modified LAS files, a format typically used for geophysical and petrophysical logs in the oil & gas and mining industries. LAS (Log ASCII Standard) files are plain text files with .las extensions. Their ASCII section normally contains depth-indexed measurements only. The provided LAS files integrate latitude and longitude as well as TVD (True Vertical Depth) so that they can be loaded independently from borehole surveys. The headers define metadata and measurement units. The Coordinate Reference System is WGS84 ellipsoid (EPSG: 4326).

The input data from passive seismic methods are continuous geophone recordings of ambient noise over extended periods of time. At Mina Concepción, two types of seismic stations were deployed: short-period and high-frequency.

Table 1. Two types of seismic stations deployed at Mina Concepción (LITHICA)

Two types of seismic stations deployed at Mina Concepcion					
Seismic station	Sensor	Datalogger	Natural Frequency	Sampling rate	Output format
Short-period	HS-1 3-C Mini Seismometer (Geospace Technologies)	SpiderNano (World Sensing)	2 Hz	100	.spd
High-frequency	Sercel Unite Cableless System		4.5 Hz	250	SEG-D (Standard for Exchange of Geophysical data)

The SpiderNano dataloggers record seismic signal in .spd format (Worldsensing internal format), while the Sercel Unite geophones produce SEG-D (Standard for Exchange of Geophysical Data) format files. Both .spd and SEG-D files were converted to MSEED (MiniSEED) file format during pre-processing and SAC (Seismic Analysis Code) format during the processing. The MSEED and the SAC file formats are widely used standards for storing seismological and geophysical time-series data. MSEED is a binary subset of the SEED (Standard for the Exchange of Earthquake Data) format, optimized for efficient storage and transmission of seismic waveform data. SAC is a specialized binary format designed for efficient processing, visualization, and interpretation of seismic waveforms. The format is optimized for compatibility with the SAC software package, which provides tools for signal analysis and processing, spectral analysis, and event detection in seismology.

Autocorrelations (AC)

AC pre-processing involved several key steps to prepare the seismic data for analysis. First, data segmentation and synchronization were performed by truncating continuous seismic traces and organizing them into individual one-day segments based on Julian days. To remove unwanted trends, mean removal and detrending were applied using a least-squares curve fitting method. Additionally, time synchronization ensured that all data traces had aligned start and end times. Next, spectral whitening was applied to enhance signal clarity and to suppress unwanted resonance energy. A specialized implementation of spectral whitening, based on Schimmel et al. (2011), was used to suppress unwanted resonance energy, particularly near-surface side lobes that could obscure geological interfaces. This process relied on a smoothed spectrum with data-specific parameters to achieve optimal performance. Finally, filtering techniques were applied to refine the data further. A Butterworth band-pass filter, covering the frequency range of 14–100 Hz, was used to enhance relevant seismic signals. Additionally, a band-reject filter between 49–51 Hz was implemented to eliminate 50 Hz electrical noise originating from nearby high-voltage transmission lines. The main processing consisted in the application of advanced computational techniques. The Phase Cross-Correlation (PCC) method (Schimmel et al., 1999) was employed, a phase-based approach that enhances time resolution while remaining amplitude-unbiased. The ACs were computed using lag times of 5 s, but the analysis was focused on identifying reflections from subsurface layers up to 1 second. Based on an assumed average seismic velocity (V_p) of 6.0–7.0 km/s, this corresponded to imaging depths of approximately 3 to 3.5 km. To enhance signal clarity, stacking techniques were applied. The autocorrelated Julian day traces were summed using a linear stack algorithm, producing a final station-specific seismic trace that improved the quality and interpretability of the recorded data. In post-processing, additional steps were carried out to refine and interpret the results. Side-lobe suppression was applied through whitening by a smoothed spectrum. This process further reduced zero-lag side lobes, which could otherwise obscure near-surface geological features. For depth estimation and geological correlation, the lag time was converted to depth using velocity assumptions, allowing for the generation of subsurface reflectivity images. These results were then compared with known well logs and geological models to validate interpretations and ensure consistency with existing geological knowledge.

Picture 7. Processing workflow for Autocorrelations LITHICA

Rayleigh Wave Ellipticity (RWE)

Before analyzing Rayleigh Wave Ellipticity (RWE), the raw seismic data underwent several pre-processing steps to ensure accurate measurements. First, the continuous three-component (3-C) seismic data were divided into 20-minute intervals to facilitate processing. To improve computational efficiency, data recorded by short-period sensors (GC stations) and nodal stations (RC stations) were decimated to sampling intervals of 0.02 s and 0.016 s, respectively, without interpolation. The selected frequency range for ellipticity analysis was 0.2–10 Hz (0.1–5 s period) to ensure the effective capture of Rayleigh wave signals. Additionally, a 5° tolerance was applied as a quality control measure to account for potential sensor tilting during installation and to mitigate the influence of contaminating signals. This ensured that only high-quality Rayleigh wave data were used in subsequent analyses. The processing of Rayleigh

Wave Ellipticity (RWE) involved extracting ellipticity and back-azimuth information from ambient seismic noise. The DOP-E method (Degree-of-Polarization Ellipticity) was applied to identify Rayleigh waves based on their characteristic elliptical motion in the vertical plane. This method enabled the detection of stable Rayleigh wave segments while filtering out noise and unwanted wave modes. Once the Rayleigh waves were identified, their ellipticity and back-azimuth (BAZ) were measured as a function of frequency and time. These measurements provided critical insights into subsurface shear-wave velocity structures. The back-azimuth distribution was also analysed to check the wave field consistency over the station array. In post-processing, a statistical analysis was performed, where the median ellipticity curve was computed for each seismic station, and absolute deviations were calculated to assess data reliability. Next, ellipticity inversion was conducted using the Neighbourhood Algorithm (NA) to derive 1D shear-wave velocity models beneath each station. Forward modelling of ellipticity was performed using Herrmann's normal mode approach, and a cost function was applied to minimize the misfit between observed and predicted ellipticity values. The best-fit models were selected based on the lowest misfit scores. Finally, the inverted velocity models were correlated with geological data and well logs to assess their accuracy.

Picture 8. Processing workflow for Rayleigh Wave Ellipticity
LITHICA

Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio (HVSr)

The pre-processing of HVSr data involved several key steps to ensure data quality. First, the continuous three-component (3-C) seismic recordings were demeaned by removing the daily mean value to eliminate long-term trends in the signals. The data were then segmented into 80-second time windows with a 50% overlap, allowing for better time resolution and signal stability. Following pre-processing, diffuse enhancement techniques were applied to the segmented data to improve signal clarity. This involved spectral whitening and normalization, following the methodology of Spica et al. (2015–2020) and Perton et al. (2018). The HVSr curves were then computed by averaging spectral ratios over 30-minute intervals, ensuring a stable representation of subsurface resonance characteristics. The final representative HVSr curve for each site was obtained by averaging individual 30-minute HVSr curves. The post-processing phase focused on statistical analysis and interpretation of HVSr curves. A broad frequency range of 0.5 to 50 Hz was analysed to capture both deep and shallow subsurface features. The study observed strong HVSr amplitude variations above 5 Hz, with additional significant features below this threshold. Anomalous HVSr amplitudes on certain days were examined, potentially linked to environmental factors such as wind or temporary human activities, which could influence data consistency. To ensure robustness, the median HVSr curve was used instead of the mean, as it is less affected by outliers.

Picture 9. Processing workflow for HVSr
LITHICA

Ambient Noise Tomography (ANT)

To carry out ANT, Rayleigh waves were extracted from continuous noise recordings, using the vertical component of the recorded seismic data. They were divided into one-hour segments, and a phase cross-correlation (PCC) method (Schimmel et al., 1999) was applied to retrieve empirical Green's functions (EGFs) from the cross-correlations of station pairs. To enhance the stability of the EGFs, the cross-correlograms were stacked daily using both a linear stacking approach and a time-frequency phase-weighted stack (tf-PWS). The extracted EGFs were analysed to obtain Rayleigh wave group velocity, which describe how surface wave velocity varies with frequency. The waveforms were filtered to extract fundamental mode Rayleigh waves, ensuring that only the most reliable signals were used for inversion. The travel times of Rayleigh waves between station pairs were measured at different frequencies, which were then used as input for a 2D tomographic inversion. The Fast-Marching Surface Tomography (FMST) algorithm (Rawlinson & Sambridge, 2005) was employed to generate a 2D velocity model for different frequencies from the measured travel times. Synthetic tests, including checkerboard tests and single anomaly tests, were conducted to assess the resolution and reliability of the inversion results. The ANT method outputs XYZ, attribute ASCII files that can be loaded directly into the AGEMERA online platform while the obtained seismic traces and velocity profiles produced by the AC, RWE and HVSR methods were converted to modified LAS files for visualization on the online platform.

2.2.4. Ground geophysical explorations

Four geophysical methods were used to improve the accuracy of identifying bauxite deposits. Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) was used to measure the variations in rock resistivity. The data for this method was collected using the Terrameter SAS 1000 and the automatic multi-electrode Lund Imaging System (LIS) from the Swedish company ABEM. The recording geometry was applied according to the target depths and the unit electrode spacing was set to 3, 5 and 10 metres. The results were processed using the inversion models of Loke and Barker (1995, 1996) to generate two-dimensional resistivity cross sections. The deviations between the observed apparent resistivities and the theoretical apparent resistivities calculated from the interpreted inverse resistivity model are given as absolute or RMS errors in per cent. The quality of the observed data is generally good and the fifth or sixth iteration is usually accepted as the solution model.

Picture 10. Example of inversion of measured data on a tomographic profile in Krstače area. The absolute error for the sixth iteration is 10.1%

UZG

In seismic methods, elastic vibrations are generated near the surface, which propagate through the subsurface and are recorded by geophones. By measuring the travel time of these waves at different distances, the velocity of wave propagation is determined, allowing the generation of a velocity model of the subsurface layers. The variation in seismic velocities helps to identify geological interfaces, as different rock types and conditions influence wave velocity. In seismic refraction surveys, geophones are placed along a profile and seismic waves are generated using a controlled source, such as a sledgehammer striking a metal plate. The first arrivals of the seismic waves are recorded and plotted in a time-distance diagram, which is used to develop a velocity model that provides information on lithological and structural relationships. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, refraction measurements were carried out at different micro-locations along some tomographic profiles with 64 geophones spaced 3 meters apart, covering profiles of 189 meters in length.

Picture 11. Geometry of P-wave recording by seismic refraction on profiles with a length of 189 m
UZG

The data collected was processed using the Delta-t-V method (Gebrande & Miller, 1985) and seismic tomography, whereby a depth penetration of up to 60 meters was achieved. However, in areas with rocks at the surface that have a high velocity and underlying deposits that have a lower velocity, a phenomenon known as “velocity inversion” can occur, making it difficult to recognize deeper deposits. To mitigate this, seismic ray coverage modelling was used to improve interpretation.

Picture 12. Inverse velocity model for the RP-8 refraction profile measured around Krstače and seismic ray coverage model
UZG

Magnetometric measurements were carried out along several tomographic profiles at the Vinjani-1, Vinjani-2, Krstače and Mratnjača-2 microsites. The measured data were corrected for daily fluctuations and micro pulsations. The measurements were carried out with synchronized GM-19T magnetometers from the Canadian company GEM System with a resolution of 0.01 nT. The distance between the magnetic observations on the magnetic profiles was 3 meters.

Picture 13. Examples of magnetic profiles around Mratnjača using measurements of the total intensity of the Earth's magnetic field. The profiles do not show magnetic anomalies originating from bauxite deposits but only anomalies from surface inhomogeneities and iron objects in the ground
 Šumanovac et al. 2024

The CSAMT (Controlled Source Audio Magnetotelluric) method is a geophysical technique that measures the ratio of the natural electric and magnetic field components at the surface to determine the resistivity of the subsurface. This impedance ratio is dependent on resistivity and frequency and allows deep penetration into the subsurface. The method is based on depolarized electrodes to measure the electric field and on magnetic coils to detect the magnetic field. Frequencies from 1 Hz to 100 kHz are used to achieve different penetration depths. As the frequency decreases, the penetration depth increases, which makes CSAMT particularly useful for exploring deeper geological structures. The method generates resistivity models that are interpreted in a similar way to electrical soundings, with variations in apparent resistivity plotted in resistivity-depth diagrams. As the Earth's natural telluric field can be distorted by external noise, an artificial electromagnetic field is often used to improve data quality, particularly for shallow investigations where higher resolution is required.

The CSAMT surveys were carried out in the Jajce area at two locations, with the soundings placed at intervals of 25 to 40 meters to ensure sufficient lateral resolution. Data acquisition was carried out using the STRATAGEM EH-4 system, with the transmitting antenna positioned at a distance of more than 250 meters to obtain a planar electromagnetic field. The recorded data was processed with the ZONDMT2D software (Zond Geophysical Software, 2012), which uses inversion algorithms to create two-dimensional resistivity models. Due to the high quality of the recorded data, both resistivity and phase difference curves were used in the inversion, although noise-related distortions in the phase data sometimes required additional filtering.

Picture 13. STRATAGEM EH-4 – Transmitting antenna for generating an artificial electromagnetic field
UZG

The data from GGMs are prepared for the AGEMERA platform as XYZ, attribute ASCII files or NetCDF datasets and PDFs with interpreted resistivity and seismic velocity cross-sections.

3. Development of Geospatial Applications

3.1. Overview of the geospatial applications (AIKPs) developed to process and visualize data sets

During the AGEMERA project, AGEMERA platform is utilized for visualization of the novel, non-invasive geophysical data for selected field trials. AGEMERA platform, developed by OPT/NET, leverages specialized AI Knowledge Packs for efficient processing, heterogeneous data fusion, and visualization of multi-dimensional geospatial data on a user-friendly web-based AGEMERA UI, with invitation curated access, enhancing mineral exploration capabilities.

Additionally, specialized AIKPs were developed during the AGEMERA project to support the geological and geophysical data integration necessary for non-invasive geophysical field trials.

3.1.1. Previously developed AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs)

As detailed in D4.3, AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs) are modular geospatial processing components that enable automated and streamline data integration, fusion and transformation into Analysis Ready Data (ARD), making processed geospatial datasets accessible via the AGEMERA UI.

Considering that AIKPs are use case specific, they facilitate the processing of heterogeneous remote sensing data, performing tasks such as unsupervised clustering analysis, PCA (Principal Component Analysis), spectral index generation, DEM (Digital Elevation Model) analysis, and RGB composite creation, among others. These AIKPs also operate on a variety of remote sensing datasets, including open-source (e.g., Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, ASTER) and commercial satellite acquisitions, ensuring flexibility across different geospatial analysis workflows.

Beyond geospatial analysis, certain AIKPs also enable the visualization and publication of data, covering various formats such as raster images, point clouds, and media files, proving an effective way of combining easily heterogeneous data coming from project partners for simple and effective visualization on a web-based AGEMERA UI platform.

Publishing Raster Data

Two dedicated AIKPs were designed to facilitate the publication of GeoTIFF raster files generated outside the OCLI backend: multiband Raster AIKP and single-band Raster AIKP.

Both AIKPs follow a structured workflow:

1. Task creation – Instantiating the AIKP template for a specific Region of Interest (ROI)
2. Parameter configuration – Setting task-specific parameters, including defining the path to the GeoTIFF file, assigning an appropriate color map for visualization, automatic min-max pixel value detection and dynamic stretching for enhanced visualization
3. Processing and publication – Generating Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG), creating and GeoJSON metadata, and publishing the dataset to AGEMERA UI.

Some of the agreed upon best practices include that GeoTIFF files provided by project partners should be in WGS84: UTM projection, 8-bit color depth, and contain transparent areas for unused regions to enhance visualization.

Publishing Media Files

The Media AIKP follows a similar workflow for publishing image-based reports, graphs, in-situ measurements and laboratory analyses and supporting documentation. It allows users to upload and visualize various file formats such as PNG, JPG, JPEG, TIFF, TIF, and PDF.

Key AIKP features include automatic detection of file type based on its extension, determination of precise geolocation. This is done by first checking and extracting geospatial coordinates from the media metadata, if the media document is geolocated. If not, possible options include centroid of the used Region of Interest polygon or users input coordinates in DMS (Degrees, Minutes, Seconds) or WGS84 decimal degree format.

Publishing Point Cloud Data

Similar to the procedures used for raster and media data, the point cloud publishing process is streamlined into a series of command-line tasks designed to convert raw point cloud files (in LAS, LAZ, or PCD formats) into analysis-ready, standardized datasets ready for the visualization on AGEMERA UI.

1. Task Creation - the workflow begins by creating a new task using the point cloud AIKP template. By invoking the command with a point cloud template, task name and the designated Region of Interest (ROI), a new task is instantiated and activated

2. Parameter Configuration - the next step involves setting the key parameters for the task. These include defining the path to the source point cloud file, specifying the projection file (for PCD formats; automatically configured for LAS/LAZ) as well as the source and output projections
3. Stack File Generation - with the task parameters in place, the system creates a normalized stack file in LAS format from the raw point cloud data. This step also generates a metadata JSON file, ensuring that all processing details are documented and stored in the default stack results folder.
4. Processing and publication – Generating 3D Model, creating and GeoJSON metadata (to ensure traceability), and publishing the dataset to AGEMERA UI.

This comprehensive workflow ensures that point cloud data is efficiently converted into a standardized, analysis-ready format and integrated into the broader AGEMERA geospatial environment.

Geospatial Analysis Using Remote Sensing Data

As part of the AGEMERA project, additional geospatial datasets were generated to complement the geophysical datasets collected during field trials. These datasets were derived from open-source satellite imagery using existing AIKPs to ensure consistency and compatibility across the analytical workflows. Used satellite data sources include optical multispectral data (i.e. Sentinel-2, ASTER) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Data (i.e. Sentinel-1).

Generated supplementary geospatial datasets include:

- RGB Composites – for example, true color, false color, geological composite image ([link to SentinelHUB](#))
- Spectral Indices – for example, NDVI, NDWI, EVI, and geological indices for Sentinel-2; NDPI and RVI for Sentinel-1 ([link to Index DataBase](#))
- Principal Component Analysis (PCA) – used for spectral dimensionality reduction and feature extraction (Jolliffe, 2002)
- SAR Change Detection – analysis of surface changes by comparing Sentinel-1 SAR images over time

These AIKPs have been instrumental in supporting geospatial analysis within AGEMERA, enabling the integration of satellite based geospatial data and geophysical data into a unified framework for visualization and interpretation.

3.1.2. Transforming and Visualizing Voxel Data using voxel AIKP

The Voxel AIKP was designed during the AGEMERA project to process, transform, and visualize voxel-based geospatial datasets, received by MUON. This module converts 3D geospatial data in NetCDF into Analysis Ready Data (ARD) formats, ensuring compatibility with visualization and analysis platforms. The output is structured in GLTF/GLB format for 3D rendering and GeoJSON for metadata storage, making it accessible through the AGEMERA User Interface (UI).

Workflow and Data Processing

The Voxel AIKP workflow follows a structured process to prepare and visualize voxel-based datasets. The main steps are outlined below and correspond to the diagram included:

1. Data Ingestion

Input data is transferred via RSYNC into the OCLI backend system, the primary geospatial processing component of the AGEMERA platform (further detailed in D4.3). Two key inputs are required: NetCDF voxel dataset (in WGS84 – UTM projection) and Region of Interest (ROI) polygon, provided in GeoJSON or KML format.

2. Task Initialization

A processing task is created using the Voxel AIKP template, specifying the input ROI and voxel dataset location.

3. 3D Model Generation

The Voxel AIKP transforms the NetCDF dataset into GLTF/GLB format, enabling interactive 3D visualization. This step ensures that voxel density and geospatial attributes are preserved.

4. Metadata Creation

A metadata file is generated in GeoJSON format, documenting transformations applied to the dataset. This ensures traceability of data processing. This metadata file, however, does not include pre-processing, inversion, or additional analytical transformations performed by partners such as MUON during prior data processing stages.

5. Data Storage and Publishing

The processed GLTF/GLB models and GeoJSON metadata are stored in a Cloud Object Storage (COS) and a database (DB). The final output is published and made available in the AGEMERA UI for interactive 3D visualization.

By following this structured workflow, the Voxel AIKP transforms NetCDF voxel datasets into 3D visualization-ready models, ensures metadata is structured and stored

in GeoJSON for accessibility and provides seamless integration with the AGEMERA UI, allowing researchers and industry users to interact with voxel-based 3D geospatial datasets.

Picture 14. Voxel AIKP workflow
OPT/NET

3.2. AGEMERA User Interfaces (AGEMERA UI) and tools

3.2.1 Examples of visualized data in AGEMERA UI

Examples of published RADAI data and how to find them in the [AGEMERA UI](#):

- Drone EM field survey in Sniznica near Posusje (Bosnia and Herzegovina) in September 2024 = “show me all in Bosnia and Herzegovina like UAV”
- Drone magnetic field survey in Rosen near Sozopol (Bulgaria) in September 2024 = “show me all in Bulgaria like UAV”
- Drone EM field surveys in 3 micro locations (2 near Mansa town, Luapula Province and Mapatizya area of Southern Province) in Zambia in 2024 = “show me all in Zambia like RADAI”

Picture 15. Electromagnetic drone measurements provided by RADAI
OPT/NET

Example of MUON subsurface muographic measurement in Jajce (Bosnia and Herzegovina) = “show me all in Bosnia and Herzegovina like MUON” supplemented with a PDF report providing geoscientific description of the voxel data.

Picture 16. Monography measurement provided by MUON OPT/NET

Example of graphs of seismic refraction profile and electrical tomography profile Bosnia and Herzegovina = **“show me all in Bosnia and Herzegovina like UZG”**

Picture 18. Ground geophysics measurement provided by UZG as media files OPT/NET

Example of georeferenced raster from 3D numerical model developed by CUP/KGHM in the Lubin mine (Poland) = **“show me all in Poland like KGHM-CUPRUM”**. A more detailed description and information about this work will be available in D4.5.

Picture 19. Distribution of the factor of safety from 3D numerical model developed by CUP/KGHM for Lubin mine (Poland) OPT/NET

EGDI database collected in and organized WPI for the field trials in the AGEMERA project is also available as a base map in the top right corner of the AGEMERA UI from

the drop-down menu. After selecting it, each country layer can be enabled in the main map view with the accompanying legend.

Picture 20. EGDI database as a base layer
OPT/NET

Lastly, examples of open optical multispectral and SAR satellite image derivatives (Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 respectively) created using specialized AIKPs = “**show me Spain / Bulgaria / Finland / Bosnia and Herzegovina / Poland / Germany / Zambia like Sentinel-1 / Sentinel-2**”

Picture 21. Example of Sentinel-2 spectral indices (upper left), unsupervised clustering of a pair of Sentinel-1 images (upper right), Sentinel-1 visualizations (middle left), Sentinel-2 RGB composites (middle right), change detection based on 2 Sentinel-1 acquisitions (lower left) and Sentinel-2 PCA (lower right)
OPT/NET

In the final months of the project, the AGEMERA UI platform will be expanded with additional datasets. These planned additions include passive seismic data from LITHICA, covering MATSA mine (Spain) and Posušje area (Bosnia and Herzegovina) sites, as well as the finalized version of muographic measurements conducted in Lubin mine (Poland). Additionally, the platform will ingest PDF reports and graphical representations of geochemical and geophysical data, aggregated from Deliverables D1.2 and D1.3. These enhancements will provide users with a more complete and integrated view of the geospatial and geological datasets available within AGEMERA.

3.2.2 Standout AGEMERA AI tools and options

The AGEMERA AI platform provides users with intuitive tools to visualize and interact with complex geological and geophysical datasets. The basic elements of AGEMERA AI are described in D4.3 in more detail, but some standout features worth mentioning are 3D viewing modes and the Lens & Multi-Lens tools, which offer a dynamic way to explore layered geospatial data. These tools simplify the process of analyzing geological structures and geophysical measurements from sources such as drone-based surveys, seismic data, and muography.

Navigating geological data in three dimensions enhances understanding and spatial awareness. The AGEMERA platform offers several viewing modes that allow users to explore data from different angles and perspectives:

- **Nadir View (Top-down View):** straightforward, bird's-eye view that provides a clear, map-like representation.
- **Camera Rotation:** allows free movement of the camera around a dataset without being anchored to a specific point.
- **World Rotation:** camera rotates around a fixed point on the ground, making it ideal for examining terrain and geological formations.
- **Helicopter Mode (Free Fly):** Offers complete freedom to move in any direction, simulating drone-like navigation for inspecting 3D objects from all sides.

These viewing modes make it easy to explore complex geological datasets in an interactive and immersive way, helping users gain deeper insights into subsurface structures and raw material deposits.

On the other hand, when analyzing multiple geospatial layers stacked on top of another, the Lens and Multi-Lens tools offer a powerful way to focus on specific information without overwhelming the visual workspace. These tools work like a "magnifying glass," allowing users to selectively view and compare different data layers by drilling through top layers of data. This means that the tool allows users to "see through" the topmost active layer while keeping other layers visible in the background. Users can pin a specific layer to be visible through the lens, ensuring a focused examination of critical data. Additional options include adjusting the lens radius with a simple slider to focus on smaller or larger sections of the dataset and reordering layers using drag-and-drop to prioritize different views.

These and many other tools allow users to seamlessly explore complex data, uncover hidden patterns, and enhance decision-making in geological analysis. The AGEMERA AI platform ensures that even advanced geospatial datasets remain accessible, interactive, and easy to interpret—without requiring expert GIS knowledge.

Picture 22. Lens and multi-lens tool in AGEMERA UI
OPT/NET

Picture 23. Additional options available in AGEMERA UI
OPT/NET

3.2.3 Data and access security

To safeguard proprietary data and control access effectively, the AGEMERA platform implements a two-tiered data security mechanism that balances openness with confidentiality.

- Invitation-Curated Platform Access

Access to the AGEMERA platform is strictly invitation-based. This ensures that only authorized users — such as project partners, technology developers, and relevant stakeholders — can explore the datasets. By curating access, the platform protects sensitive geological and geophysical data, preventing unauthorized viewing or misuse.

- Role-Based Data Visibility

Once inside the platform, users are assigned to different groups, determining what data they can view. General Public users can only access open-source datasets, such as Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, ASTER, and their derivatives while Consortium Members have broader privileges, allowing them to visualize additional proprietary datasets published within the platform.

In all cases, data owners retain full control over their datasets, choosing whether to make them available to specific user groups or restrict access entirely.

This layered security approach makes AGEMERA platform an ideal platform for technology developers and mining companies alike. Technology developers can demonstrate their novel geophysical and AI-driven methods in a secure environment, without exposing sensitive mine location data. Mining operators can use the platform for monitoring, data fusion, and decision-making, knowing that their proprietary datasets remain protected from unauthorized access. Since data is never downloadable, even within the platform, companies and researchers can share insights without the risk of data leaks.

By combining strict access control with flexible data visibility settings, AGEMERA platform ensures that users can benefit from cutting-edge geospatial technology while safeguarding sensitive geological information.

Conclusion

The AGEMERA platform is designed to streamline geological surveys and enhance the commercial viability of the technology by making it easier for mining companies to identify areas of interest for CRM extraction. It marks a significant advancement by integrating a wide range of geophysical and remote sensing datasets into a single, user-friendly interface, the platform enables a detailed and interactive visualization of subsurface structures that are critical for identifying potential mineral deposits.

Throughout this deliverable, we have demonstrated how advanced processing techniques—including AI-driven data transformation, 3D voxel modelling, and comprehensive data fusion—can convert complex raw data into precise, analysis-ready formats.

The integrated approach presented in this deliverable lays a strong foundation for both current applications and future innovations, reinforcing the AGEMERA platform's potential to transform the way mineral exploration is conducted. Looking ahead, the ongoing refinement of the AGEMERA UI and its associated AI Knowledge Packs (AIKPs) promises to further empower users with robust analytical tools.

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